

Ordered and Secured

To start with, personal medical data is private and strictly protected. However, progress cannot be made in medicine without human data. The solution is a data management software program that provides security and only grants access to authorised material.

Data on the human genome should be treated with the utmost care and complying with information security protocols. In order to ensure information security, ELIXIR provides a service in which researchers log into a system that identifies their electronic identity while also distributing access rights to the biomedical data stored in the cloud. In this way, the researcher creates a secure analysis environment for the data to be analysed. This is made possible by the REMS tool.

ELIXIR strictly adheres to the EU law on information security. When researchers utilise data, the REMS tool can be used to ensure that the shared data is subject to authorisation.

“REMS is an access management tool that, where necessary, prevents the illegal use of data.”

CSC, the Finnish ELIXIR node, develops and maintains the open source REMS tool that can be used to manage access to datasets containing confidential material. REMS (Resource Entitlement Management System) is an access management tool that, where necessary, prevents the illegal use of data. With the REMS tool, it is possible to order a specific file from a large amount of data and have it delivered to the ordering party locked in a secure manner.

“There may be various tools within an organisation handling similar things. Although there are many ready-made tools and services available for identity and role management, I have not heard of any other general resource entitlement software like REMS”, says the REMS tool’s product owner Tommi Jalkanen from CSC.

ELIXIR AAI: a federation of 200 organisations

REMS is part of a federated system formed by the ELIXIR community comprising nearly 200 organisations. Becoming a federation has required agreements between the different organisations regarding information security, personal data law, rights and

ELIXIR AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure) is a federation of user identities and access rights. First, get an ELIXIR identity. Second, apply for software, storage and compute, and data access authorisation if the data resource is protected. Your service and data access authorisation is stored and travels with your electronic identity relying on REMS service. With this attribute attached to your electronic identity, you can open a database or start a virtual machine. Permission is granted by the service provider.

First identify yourself. Where are you from?
What is your email? Where do you work?
Does your employer vouch for you?

AAI REMS Request
access to data
sets with REMS
(Resource Entitlement
Management System)

Cloud & Compute provided
by ELIXIR-nodes from
21 countries and EMBL

Scientific
software
environment

Virtual
Services and
cloud storage

The ELIXIR compute platform provides a seamless workflow for users: the researchers may use their electronic identity to securely create a scientific software analysis environment, and gain access to large sensitive biological data resources stored on a cloud. The platform also helps research groups to create scalable services.

Why monitoring access rights is important

Using statistical methods, it is possible to identify a person with sufficient probability from anonymised material if genomic information is available on the subject. Therefore, this issue must be approached through information security, the usage agreements of the service providing genomic data as well as national and international legislation.

If the anonymised material is linked with additional information, such as year of birth or the name of the disease, the researcher must be reliably authenticated in the service and accept the service's terms of use, which prohibit the identification of the persons included in the materials. It is also possible to profile users, in which case each profile can be provided with an appropriate view of the material. The access rights and legislation define how the materials should be, for example, stored and analysed.

Ari Turunen

MORE INFORMATION:

CSC – IT Center for Science

is a non-profit, state-owned company administered by the Ministry of Education and Culture. CSC maintains and develops the state-owned, centralised IT infrastructure.

<http://www.csc.fi>

<https://research.csc.fi/cloud-computing>

ELIXIR

builds infrastructure in support of the biological sector. It brings together the leading organisations of 21 European countries and the EMBL European Molecular Biology Laboratory to form a common infrastructure for biological information. CSC – IT Center for Science is the Finnish centre within this infrastructure.

<http://www.elixir-finland.org>

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